

Patients Dissociative for Interventions That Could Help Solve Possession of an Identity That Could Facilitate the Emergence of Identities Critical to the Alternative and Therapeutic Process

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Abstract

dissociative patients to practice spontaneous hypnosis and some control over self-hypnosis may allow them to control certain distressing symptoms and use their hypnotic abilities to ease constructive self-care strategies. One formulation of this problem is that dissociative patients use various self-hypnosis strategies in an uninvited, uncontrolled, and unregulated way, often without

realizing it. DID therapy have found a place for a variety of techniques based on the DID patient's self-hypnotic abilities; these techniques can be used with or without formal trance induction (RP Kluft , 1982, 1988a, 1989, 1994; Phillips & Frederick, 1995). These techniques include access to alternative identities that are not at once available, an intervention that may facilitate the emergence of identities critical to the therapeutic process, and/or help resolve the situation of having a "stuck" infantile, disoriented, or dysfunctional identity. A related strategy, known as restructuring, involves "reorganizing" a system of alternative identities that is in a dysfunctional state of disequilibrium. This is done by asking various identities to play important roles in a safer and more stable constellation. Other hypnotherapeutic techniques are designed to modulate affect , explore and resolve disturbing psychological problems, control flashbacks and processing of reactions and traumatic memories, and control flashbacks and processing of interruptions and traumatic memories. To place unstable identities in settings away from the mental mainstream to preserve somatoform symptoms , functions, and safety, to put identities into a therapeutic "sleep" between sessions, to restore overall rebalance, to encourage identities to communicate and to interact constructively with one another (e.g., Fraser's , 2003), the dissociative table technique) and promoting or ensuring integration. It is important to place somatoform symptoms and unresolved identities in settings away from the mental mainstream (for example, fusion rituals) to preserve function. For example, during Stage 2 (which deals with the treatment of traumatic memories), hypnotic techniques such as internally visualizing memories on a controllable screen can help regulate and modulate the impact of the memory on the person.

Keywords: *Dissociative patients, DID, DID symptoms , Psychological Disorders, DID Symptoms, DID Treatment*

1. Introduction

"Split-screen" techniques can help with cognitive restructuring of traumatic events, and judicious use of regression techniques (keeping in mind the difficulties of memory) can be helpful when recalling past events. In phase 3 (reintegration and rehabilitation), hypnotic techniques can help reinforce a harmonious sense of self in the present. This is possible, for example, by rehearsing

probable future events (Cardeña , Maldonado , et al ., 2009) in a way that avoids recurrence. Because people with DID are capable of self-hypnosis, many hypnotic techniques can be used effectively throughout DID treatment, although formal trance induction is not necessary. Patients may be instructed to use at least some of these strategies outside of the therapist 's office, which is an advantage.

2. First Stage of Treatment

Phase 1 of treatment, autohypnotic techniques can be particularly helpful to supply relaxation, allow the patient to use an imaginary safe place to soothe himself, alleviate various symptoms , aid dysphoric moods through the use of ego-strengthening suggestions . Supplying better coping skills, active awake hypnosis, etc. Creating the ability to "ground" the present time by using it is a separate consideration. These techniques can also help relieve a variety of symptoms . In later stages, added autohypnotic skills can be taught. Some examples of these skills include the ability to have traumatic memories and the use of an internally visualized location as a "meeting place" that enables identities to discuss and problem-solve problems and everyday concerns. Clinicians should be aware of the current controversy about the use of hypnosis in trauma treatment, particularly the use of hypnosis-facilitated techniques to explore areas of amnesia or to further explore fragmented images or memories of the traumatic event (D. Brown et al ., 1998).

point to the recovery of material confirmed later (RP Kluft , 1995) and therapeutic progress usually achieved with hypnotic techniques. However, the undesirable clinical consequences attributed to hypnosis are likely to be based more on misleading cues and other misuses of hypnosis than on hypnosis itself. Evidence suggests that obscene interventions, such as misleading questions rather than hypnosis itself, lead to memory distortions, particularly in populations most likely to be hypnotized (McConkey , 1992) (Scoboria , Mazzoni , and Kirsch , 2006). (McConkey , 1992). Like other interventions, hypnotherapy should only be used with adequate training, both in the method itself and in its specific use in traumatized and dissociative patients. In addition to being highly hypnotizable, some DID patients were thought to be highly prone to fantasy (Lynn , Rhue , & Green , 1988). (Lynn , Rhue and Green , 1988). A minority may be so, but several studies

suggest that most DID patients are only moderately prone to fantasy (Williams, Loewenstein , & Gleaves , 2004). However, there are concerns that at least some DID patients, with or without hypnosis, are vulnerable to mixing fantasy with real memories and/or confusing experiences in the inner worlds of personalities with events in external reality (RP Kluft , 1998). (RP Kluft , 1998). Therefore, therapists who use hypnosis in an exploratory way should limit the number of leading questions they ask and avoid cues and pressures that have the potential to distort the characteristics of what is remembered while under the influence of hypnosis.

Hypnosis may also leave patients an unwarranted level of confidence in those recalled in hypnotic situations, although there is evidence that giving specific informed consent on this latter issue can reduce this overconfidence (see Cardea , Maldonado , et al., 2009). If a therapist plans to use hypnosis or any other specialized technique with a patient, they must obtain appropriate informed consent from the patient beforehand . This approval should cover the potential benefits, risks, and limitations of the technique in question, as well as ongoing discussions of the technique. Informed consent should also include possible restrictions on the admissibility of testimony in legal settings regarding memories obtained under hypnosis. These restrictions should be based on laws and judgments in the jurisdiction in which the therapist practices and should be applied to memories obtained under hypnosis (American Society of Clinical Hypnosis, 1994).

3. EMDR

EMDR is an acronym for eye movement desensitization and reprocessing. It was first set up in 1989 and has since gained popularity for its ability to accelerate the resolution of traumatic memories in patients with uncomplicated PTSD (Shapiro , 1989) . However, early use of standard EMDR for patients with unrecognized DID has resulted in serious clinical problems such as unintended violations of resolution barriers, overflow, sudden emergence of undiagnosed alternative identities, and rapid destabilization. These problems led to several serious clinical complications (Lazrove & Fine , 1996; Paulsen , 1995; Shapiro , 1995; Young, 1994). As a result of this, practitioners are now strongly encouraged to evaluate each client for the presence and degree of dissociation before beginning any EMDR therapy , regardless of the nature of the current

problem. In addition, the current professional opinion is that original EMDR procedures should be changed for safe and successful use in DPD patients (Beere , 2009; Fine , 2009; Forgash & Knipe , 2008; Gelinias , 2003; Paulsen , 2008; Twombly , 2005; Van der Hart et al. , 2006). (Beere , 2009; Fine , 2009; Forgash & Knipe , 2008; Gelinias , 2003; Paulsen , 2008; Twombly , 2005; Van der Hart et al, 2006). EMDR has many potential benefits in the treatment of DID. These include a consistent set of manual interventions to change traumatic distortions in one's self-representation and increase relational connections .

4. Facilitating the Integration of Processed Traumatic Material into Alternative Identities (Fine , 2009; Gelinias , 2003; Twombly , 2005).

EMDR is useful for the development of new behaviors because it allows individuals to process their earlier traumatic experiences and current triggers and can then create new templates of desired abilities or behaviors. This speeds up the process.

Recommended Guidelines:

The General Guide to the Use of EMDR in Dissociative Disorders (written by the EMDR Dissociative Disorders Task Force and published by Shapiro , 1995, 2001) offers several recommendations. The guideline recommends integrating EMDR therapy into a comprehensive treatment plan rather than using it as a stand-alone treatment option . Only clinicians familiar with the treatment of dissociative disorders should use EMDR procedures and only after evaluating the patient's readiness for EMDR processing of traumatic material. If a dissociative disorder is present, only clinicians familiar with the treatment of dissociative disorders should use EMDR procedures . The EMDR procedure is only recommended when the patient is generally stable and has adequate coping skills, adequate internal cooperation between alternative identities, and the ability to maintain the dual awareness focus required in EMDR procedures (Forgash & Knipe , 2008; Gelinias , 2003). ; Lazrove & Fine , 1996; Paulsen , 1995; Twombly , 2005). (Forgash and Knipe , 2008; Gelinias , 2003; Lazrove and Fine , 1996; Paulsen , 1995; Twombly , 2005).

Contraindications to the use of eye movement desensitization and reprocessing include continued abusive relationship(s), strong opposition to processing by alternative identities, and serious comorbid diagnoses such as psychosis, active substance abuse, or severe character pathology . An assistive technique such as modified EMDR may be helpful in the treatment of dissociative identity disorder (DID). Paulsen (1995), Lazrove and Fine (1996), and Twombly (2000) were the first to present the concepts of how EMDR could be used in the treatment of dissociative disorders. An innovative stage-oriented model was presented by Fine and Berkowitz (2001). This model uses the high hypnotizability of the DID patient to replace hypnotherapy techniques with modified EMDR procedures . This makes it possible to safely handle and integrate traumatic material as the patient is repeatedly stabilized . Modified EMDR procedures, placed in the general phase-oriented framework, can be used when and when appropriate to work on specific traumatic materials, with the potential to reduce the risks of early exposure and overactivation to traumatic memories (Fine & Berkowitz , 2001) . ; Forgash & Knipe , 2008; Brides , 2003; Paulsen , 2008; Twombly , 2005). (Fine & Berkowitz , 2001; Forgash & Knipe , 2008; Gelinas , 2003; Paulsen , 2008; Twombly , 2005).

The EMDR Institute Training Manual (Shapiro , 2009) currently covers multiple EMDR treatments in three phases of the phase-oriented approach. Clinicians combined EMDR therapies for symptom reduction and control, ego building, working with alternative identities, and, where appropriate, permission negotiation and preparation of alternative identities for modified EMDR processing of traumatic memories. Numerous treatments involve working with other identities and problem solving during processing (Fine & Berkowitz , 2001; Forgash & Knipe , 2008; Gelinas , 2003, 2009; Paulsen , 2008, 2009; Twombly & Schwartz, 2008); using the Korn

these therapies are first used to help stabilize, but ultimately also help control the processing of particularly fearful traumatic memories (Fine & Berkowitz , 2001; Paulsen , 1995; Twombly , 2005). (Fine & Berkowitz , 2001; Paulsen , 1995; Twombly , 2005). When using EMDR with DID patients, it is vital to limit the dangers of crossing dissociation lines and spilling over. As highlighted by Van der Hart et al. (2006), " The danger with using EMDR in persistently traumatized people is that it typically reactivates too many traumatic memories too quickly" (p. 327). (p. 327). Associative processing, which is the act of allowing the process to bridge with

associated memories, is not encouraged in DID patients, unlike the typical EMDR procedure . This is done to keep material quantity and density at a manageable level (Fine & Berkowitz , 2001; Lazrove & Fine , 1996; Paulsen , 1995; Twombly , 2005). Instead, target memory should be procedurally isolated to the greatest extent possible.

5. To Modulate the Intensity of EMDR Study

Various techniques have been developed to modulate the intensity of EMDR work, including piecewise abreaction and serial desensitization, which involve processing different elements of a memory held by separate self-states (Fine & Berkowitz , 2001; Lazrove & Fine , 1996; Paulsen , 2008; Rouanzoin , 2007). (Fine & Berkowitz , 2001; Lazrove & Fine , 1996; Paulsen , 2008; Rouanzoin , 2007). Other protective changes of EMDR for DID include the rate and type of alternating bilateral stimulation for extremely dissociative individuals. Many clinicians are of the opinion that shorter sets of alternating bilateral stimulation (Lazrove & Fine , 1996; Paulsen , 1995; Wesselman , 2000) and bilateral stimulation with auditory or tactile alternation are better tolerated by dissociative patients than the use of eye movements (Bergmann , 2008). ; Forgash and Knipe , 2008). (Bergmann , 2008; Forgash & Knipe , 2008). Longer sessions may be required, not because patients need to be exposed to more traumatic information, but rather so that clinicians can give patients the opportunity to process and integrate the information at a pace within their tolerance range and stabilize patients before time expires (Van der Hart et al., 2006). It is important for clinicians to be aware that the processing of a memory for DID patients will often be incomplete during an EMDR session. The need to revisit and reprocess target memories may represent either the natural next step in some of the memory to be addressed, or the patient's newly developed ability to process and integrate previously unbearable memories.

6. Expressive and Rehabilitation Treatment Modalities

Expressive and rehabilitation therapies are often an integral part of inpatient, partial, inpatient and outpatient treatments for patients with DID . Modalities such as art therapy, horticultural therapy,

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journaling, music therapy, movement therapy, occupational therapy, poetry therapy, psychodrama, and therapeutic recreation provide the patient with unique opportunities to address a wide variety of therapeutic issues within a structured and supportive context. Expression through creative arts or expression therapies can take place in a one-on-one setting with one therapist or in a group setting with multiple therapists. Each modality provides a different medium or format in which people can safely communicate their underlying thoughts and feelings to one another. Nonverbal processes and outcomes (eg , artwork , musical expression, dance sequences, writing, etc.) can serve as a visible or written record of the experiences of the internal systems of different identities and can be reviewed at any time in therapy. Expressive therapies are especially helpful in the healing process because vital information about current stressors, triggers, safety issues, previous traumatic experiences, and coping strategies are often spoken nonverbally long before they are voiced.

This makes expressive therapies particularly useful. Works of art, writings, music, etc. The following discussion can be used for a variety of therapeutic goals. In conjunction with verbal associations, nonverbal psychotherapeutic approaches bridge the communication gap between fragmented parts of the self and between the patient's inner world and outer reality. Additionally, in both group and individual settings, expressive therapy helps patients develop focus, fact-based thinking, internal organization and cooperation, problem-solving abilities, and their ability to use restraint strategies.

Creative therapies have the potential to foster insight, the glorification of anger and other intense emotions, and the in-depth study of traumatic experiences. In addition, creative therapies can help with the goal of integration . Many psychotherapists find patients' drawings and diaries useful in continuing treatment, in addition to their function of describing diagnostic difficulties. Established by Cohen, Mills , and Kijak (1994), the Diagnostic Drawing Series is one of the standardized art tests typically used to arrive at the differential diagnosis of DID . Its specificity for use in dissociative individuals has also been demonstrated (Mills & Cohen, 1993). (Mills & Cohen, 1993). In patients diagnosed with DID, rehabilitation therapies such as occupational therapy , horticultural therapy, and therapeutic recreation can be particularly helpful in improving overall functioning. The patient's capacity to perform activities in a reliable and age-appropriate manner

is documented through the provision of structured, fact-based crafts or tasks alongside ongoing functional assessments. Occupational therapy tests can also provide data on how daily life, personal hygiene, food preparation, money management, employment, education, leisure/unstructured time, and social life may be adversely affected by dissociative symptoms.

therapists operating in inpatient, partial, inpatient and outpatient settings are normally graduate or doctoral level clinicians and are board certified and/or registered in their profession; they may also be licensed in assistive mental health fields.

patients to bring artwork to therapy sessions and/or for clinicians to occasionally ask individuals to create art, the formal use of expression and rehabilitation therapies as part of the therapy assignment should only be practiced by clinicians with appropriate training and certification. Sensory-motor Psychotherapy Treatment of DID is difficult because of the wide variety of impairments in sensation, perception, autonomic control, and movement. Sensorimotor psychotherapy combines traditional speech therapy techniques with body-centered interventions that directly address these neurobiological and somatoform dissociative symptoms of trauma (Ogden et al., 2006). Direct somatic therapies help the patient regain their capacity to manage the disordered physiological states that lead to dissociation.

7. Sensory-Motor Psychotherapy Is Essentially Integrative

Sensori-motor psychotherapy is essentially integrative and prevents iatrogenic worsening of personality dissociation. This is because one's body is a common whole for all identities. Paying attention to how the body moves and feels can both educate the therapist about the client's history of traumatic experiences and introduce them to the physical postures, gestures, and emotions unique to each identity, while also providing opportunities to break these patterns. sensorimotor that alerts the patient to somatic and physiological indicators of change Therapies are often the first signs of change and can be very helpful in helping the patient gain control over the change. For the use of sensorimotor psychotherapy in the treatment of phase-oriented trauma for ICD, it is necessary to understand how to intervene at the bodily level for each phase of treatment. This

includes teaching somatic skills to facilitate stability and symptom reduction in Stage 1, maintaining the patient's general balance while attempting to complete actions and integrating traumatic memory in Stage 2, and teaching physical actions that promote greater integration and adaptation in normal life.

8. Directed Awareness

Sensory-motor psychotherapy with an emphasis on the use of "directed awareness" can assist in the restoration of a witnessing self and ultimately assist patients in identifying attributes of identities present in the here and now. Sensory-motor psychotherapy, unlike most body-centered therapies, allows the practice of physical touch as an option, but it is not an inherently "hands-on" approach. As a result, it is suitable for use with clients suffering from dissociative disorder and is easy to incorporate into more traditional psychotherapeutic models. Because of the severe anxiety that many people with DID have about their own bodies and physical contact with other people, this method should be used with caution and at the appropriate time. Clinicians, sensorimotor Before attempting to apply therapy techniques, they must ensure that they have a thorough understanding of the phase-oriented paradigm of DID treatment. Electroconvulsive Therapy (ECT) Although ECT has not been shown to be an effective or acceptable treatment for dissociative disorders, it may be helpful in treating a comorbid refractory condition.

163 depressions on DID (Bowman & Coons, 1992; DeBattista, Solvason, & Spiegel, 1998)—also known as double depression, which describes a major depressive episode consistently superimposed on a depressive base. (Bowman and Coons, 1992; DeBattista, Solvason, and Spiegel, 1998) (Klein, Taylor, Harding, and Dickstein, 1988). In cases of double depression caused by ICD, the presence of melancholy and/or true psychotic symptoms is a better indicator of how well ECT will work. Like other patients undergoing ECT, a subset of DID patients report significant permanent autobiographical memory loss and persistent memory impairment after ECT. This memory impairment is superimposed (and can be difficult to distinguish) on chronic complex dissociative amnesia. ECT patients also report significant permanent autobiographical memory loss. Electroconvulsive for dissociative identity disorder (DID) Informed consent for

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therapy (ECT) should address these challenges in addition to the informed consent considerations typical for ECT.

In the past, prior to the development of clinical and psychometric assessment tools, hypnosis and/or pharmacologically facilitated interviews (most commonly using amobarbital (Amytal)) were used to aid in the diagnosis and treatment of dissociative disease. These interviews have also been used for the differential diagnosis and treatment of acute conversion disorders and diffuse dissociative amnesia, among other things (Naples & Hackett , 1978). However, the use of amobarbital and other pharmaceuticals with similar properties may pose a risk to the health of some people. Some of the possible side effects of these drugs include drowsiness, hypotension, loss of coordination and allergic responses. Pharmacologically assisted interviews are classified as "conscious sedation", according to current criteria set by the Joint Commission on the Accreditation of Healthcare Organizations in the United States . For this reason, these treatments can only be performed within the boundaries of the hospital, which is equipped with the necessary monitoring and safety standards used by the anesthesia department of the hospital. It is possible that administrative norms in other countries are different in this regard, but even if they are different, these processes are still unusual outside the United States. As a result, currently pharmacologically assisted interviews are not frequently used in the diagnosis or treatment processes for dissociative identity disorder (DID). One type of dissociative disorder is known as dissociative identity disorder (DID), once called multiple personality disorder. Many people with dissociative identity disorder have had a difficult upbringing that can cause them to leave their bodies as a way of coping with the tremendous trauma they have experienced.

The presence of at least two additional separate personalities is one of the symptoms of dissociative identity disorder (DID). Other symptoms include feeling disconnected from the person's sense of self. Memory loss is a common symptom of dissociative identity disorder (DID), which occurs when different people take control. DID is one of the most misunderstood conditions in the field of psychiatry. It is important to dispel common misconceptions about this condition by citing credible studies to raise awareness and reduce the associated social stigma.

9. DID Has Been Documented For Hundreds Of Years

Despite popular belief, DID is not a real condition. There is a common misconception that dissociative identity disorder (DID) is a temporary "medical fad", not a real illness. On the other hand, DID has been documented for hundreds of years and has an important place in the relevant medical literature. Patients with this condition may have two or more separate personality states coexisting within the same physical body. These identities may have different names, features, voices and behaviors. Memory loss is a common symptom of dissociative identity disorder (DID). According to research conducted and published in 2014, dissociative identity disorder is a complex but real disorder that can be demonstrated by many different indicators.

10. Studies According to Reliable Sources

DPD is associated with various brain areas as well as cognitive abilities. It is not difficult to distinguish the symptoms of DID from the symptoms of other disorders. The illness is often linked to acute emotional trauma in early relationships. As a result of the decline after the increase in the number of diagnoses during the 1980s and 1990s, dissociative identity disorder (DID) has become a medical fad. Some people think it was once common practice to diagnose people with the condition and that at some point it went out of style. However, cases of DID have been reported in the medical literature for hundreds of years, according to the findings of Trusted Source researchers. In addition, experts reported that 1,339 research publications on DID were written between 2000 and 2014. This demonstrates the continuing interest of professionals in the disease. Other evidence that contradicts this misunderstanding includes:

- *Patients diagnosed with IPD are reliably found in inpatient, outpatient, and community samples collected from around the world.*

The diagnosis of DID can be made with a high level of accuracy through clinical practice as well as structured or semi-structured interviews. Psychotherapy that addresses trauma and dissociation is often helpful for those with dissociative identity disorder (DID). DID is relatively easily distinguishable from various other mental health conditions. Both borderline personality disorder

(BPD) and post- traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) are possible conditions that co-occur with dissociative identity disorder (DID) (PTSD).

The myth that ICD is a relatively rare disease The belief that ICD is a relatively rare condition is common and can even be found in some introductory psychology texts. It may seem otherwise, based on prevalence statistics in both the general population and psychiatric settings. In fact, DID is much more common than schizophrenia. According to the study's findings, DID is found in approximately 1.1% to 1.5% of population samples.

In contrast, anywhere between 0.25% and 0.64% of adults are believed to suffer from schizophrenia. Of a sample population of 658 people from New York, 1.5% met the diagnostic criteria for ICD. In a study conducted on 628 women in the society in Turkey, 1.1% of them were found to have IPD. Studies looking at communities that have experienced unusually high levels of trauma or cultural oppression reveal that dissociative identity disorder (DID) is the most common. For example, in a highly traumatic inner-city sample in the United States, 6% of patients admitted to multiple hospitals were diagnosed with ICD.

The myth that dissociative identity disorder and schizophrenia are the same thing Contrary to popular assumption, dissociative identity disorder and schizophrenia are two separate mental illnesses. The belief that a person with schizophrenia has a "split personality" - the concept that the self is split into several identities - remains a common but inaccurate misconception about this disorder.

A 2008 survey by the National Alliance on Mental Illness (NAMI) showed that 64 percent of respondents thought "split or multiple personalities" were symptoms of schizophrenia. Recent attempts at mental health have tried to educate people on the distinction between the two, but the misconception persists. The fact that DID symptoms often overlap with the positive symptoms of schizophrenia, such as a change in perspective on reality, is another factor that contributes to the persistence of this misperception. However, people with DID are also less likely to have negative symptoms of schizophrenia, such as withdrawal from social situations or an inability to enjoy activities they previously enjoyed. People with schizophrenia have a lower risk of experiencing dissociative symptoms , such as forgetting who they are and losing memories . This is an additional

critical difference. Schizophrenia is an inherited disorder that usually runs in families and, if left untreated, can lead to a steady decline in a person's level of functioning. Schizophrenia is a disease that can also be inherited. Trauma is the most common trigger of dissociative identity disorder (DID), rather than genetics.

11. DID Not a Personality Condition

A personality problem can be caused by DID. However, dissociative identity disorder (DID) is not a personality condition contrary to popular belief. The DSM-5 classifies dissociative disorder (DID) as a dissociative disorder. People may have this misconception that DID is a personality disorder for a number of different reasons . Although renamed dissociative identity disorder in 1994, some people still call it "multiple personality disorder." This can lead to misunderstanding. Another explanation is that those who suffer from borderline personality disorder are more likely to have DID .

Although the two diseases have common symptoms (as with many diseases), they can be distinguished from each other because each has its own characteristics. Memory lapses and a general feeling of disconnection from one's body and the outside world are symptoms associated with dissociative disorders . Personality disorders are characterized by a repetitive pattern of traits that impair an individual's ability to lead a normal life.

DID are more likely to be aggressive The relationship between IPD and an increase in violent behavior has not been conclusively demonstrated by research. Horror movies depicting characters with dissociative identity disorder (DID) have helped perpetuate this misconception and can even be blamed for starting it. The diagnosis of DID is controversial because of the notion that criminals would not be punished if they claimed to have committed the crime by another person, according to research by the Trusted Source in 2009 .

However, there is no association between DID and an increase in criminal activity. Participants were minimally involved in the legal system, according to the findings of a 2017 study of 173 patients treated for dissociative identity disorder by a reliable source. The findings of the study

showed that only 0.6% of the population was locked up in the previous six months. In addition, there were no convictions or probation notices in the previous six months.

12. Conclusion

they concluded that none of the IPD symptoms accurately predicted criminal behavior. The misconception that people with dissociative identity disorder (DID) pose a threat contributes to the constant stigma of people with the condition. To reconsider, dissociative identity disorder (DID) is a widely misunderstood psychiatric condition. The stigma faced by many people living with DID can be alleviated in part by dispelling common myths. A better understanding of dissociative identity disorder (DID) and the reduction of the stigma associated with it could lead to an increase in the number of people living with DID who feel comfortable seeking help or receiving treatment, which can ultimately result in such a life. The diagnosis of dissociative identity disorder (DID) is often considered the most challenging of all psychiatric disorders. Getting a diagnosis for many completely mismatched conditions is one of the "clues" to pointing to dissociative identity disorder (DID). Before realizing I have dissociative identity disorder (DID), I had previously been mistakenly diagnosed with borderline personality disorder (BPD), attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), and bipolar disorder. In fact, I didn't get an accurate diagnosis of dissociative identity disorder until after I had an episode of dissociative amnesia that lasted for two years. (This is when a person experiences one or more episodes of being unable to remember important information, typically as a result of a traumatic experience or stressful situation .) One of the most severe forms of dissociative disorders is dissociative identity disorder (DID). A dissociative disorder is diagnosed when an individual's tendency to leave becomes a persistent reaction to one or more traumatic experiences. DID is a condition in which a person's identity is split between two or more personality states, also known as alters. This condition was formerly known as multiple personality disorder. Additional common symptoms may include: dissociative amnesia memory problems not caused by any known medical condition dissociative fugue is a mental condition in which a person wanders aimlessly and is unable to remember their own personal information. a feeling that one's identity is in shambles According to the APA, ninety

percent of people with DID have been the target of systematic abuse or neglect during their developmental years . Symptoms One of the reasons dissociative identity disorder (DID) is so difficult to diagnose is that many of the symptoms overlap with other illnesses.

- a. *Below is a list of symptoms that I personally experience regularly :*
- b. *Amnesia or memory loss in a dissociative context*
 - i. *Depersonalization and derealization*
 - ii. *A feeling of alienation from both myself and my feelings*
 - iii. *extreme and sudden changes in mood*
 - iv. *Hypersensitivity to being overwhelmed, blurred, or other personalities coming and going depending on the amount of stress, or mixed sense of self, or significant strain in relationships within the family*

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